

Prediction of physical parameters of F Type Stars listed in the X-Shooter Stellar Library by Neural Network algorithm created on the features, identified using PHOENIX Model grid.

**Project Report
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1. Introduction

Determination of the stellar parameters of a star is of paramount importance in understanding the physics going deep inside the stellar atmosphere. The task is undoubtedly challenging because of several factors. One of which is that stars are very distant, therefore their radiation suffers severe absorption by the interstellar dust and gas medium as well as atmospheric noises itself present in our earth. This makes the job of determining the stellar parameters accurately, a field of research on its own merit. Since the beginning of the study of astrophysics, when the first spectrograph was made, several strides has been taken in the direction of stellar spectroscopy and hence our knowledge of stellar atmospheres have grown to a broader extent.

The late 20th century has marked a significant evolution in computational stellar spectroscopy, driven by advances in computational power, numerical methods, and the development of sophisticated models of stellar atmospheres. Research in this field has focused on improving the precision of spectral analysis, developing detailed models for various types of stars, and applying these models to understand stellar structure, evolution, and chemical composition. In the late 20th century, the field began to focus on the development of 1D stellar atmosphere models. These models treat the star as a spherically symmetric body and assume hydrostatic equilibrium, radiative transfer, and local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE). Kurucz (1979) developed a comprehensive set of model atmospheres for various stellar types, which became a cornerstone for stellar spectroscopy. [1] Dimitri Mihalas (1978, 1984) made significant contributions to the development of computational methods for radiative transfer and the construction of model atmospheres. [2] [3] As computational power increased, researchers began to explore models that relax the assumption of LTE, leading to more accurate representations of stellar atmospheres, particularly for hot stars where departures from LTE are significant. The work by Ivan Hubeny and Thierry Lanz (1995) [4] on the TLUSTY code represents a significant advancement in the ability to model the spectra of hot stars with complex atomic species and line blanketing effects. The late 1990s and early 2000s saw the development of 3D hydrodynamic models of stellar atmospheres, which account for convective motions and provide a more realistic description of stellar surfaces as shown by Asplund et al. (2000) [5] and Nordlund et al. (2009). [6]

As computational methods improved, the focus shifted to applying stellar atmosphere models to large populations of stars. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in applying machine learning and data-driven approaches to the analysis of stellar spectra, driven by the wealth of data from large-scale surveys. The 21st century has seen a rapid expansion in the application of machine learning (ML) techniques in stellar spectroscopy, driven by the increasing availability of large datasets from astronomical surveys and advances in computational power. These ML techniques have been used for a wide range of applications, including the automated classification of stellar spectra, determination of stellar parameters, chemical abundance analysis, and the identification of unique stellar populations. The classification of stellar spectra, traditionally a manual and labour-intensive process, has been greatly enhanced by ML algorithms, particularly through the use of supervised and unsupervised learning methods. (Bailer-Jones et al. (2001), Fiorentin et al. (2007)). [7] [8]

ML techniques have been extensively used to estimate stellar parameters such as effective temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity from spectral data. In the early 2000s, Coryn A. L. Bailer-Jones and colleagues pioneered the use of artificial neural networks (ANNs) for the automated classification of stellar spectra and the determination of stellar parameters. (Bailer-Jones et al. (2000, 2001)). [7] Neves et al (2014) [9] developed a method of least square fitting of equivalent widths of the spectral lines in 530 – 690 nm range to predict effective temperatures and metallicities, and achieved an RMSE of 0.12 dex for metallicity and 293 K for temperature. Newton et al. (2015) [10] developed a calibration method for effective temperatures, radii, and bolometric luminosities using Mg and Al spectral features in low-resolution near-infrared spectra. Mann et al. (2015) [11] employed classical χ^2 minimization to match observed optical spectra to synthetic spectra from the CIFIST2011 library for calculating effective

temperatures. For metallicity, EWs of atomic lines in near-infrared spectra were used, based on calibrations from wide binaries. Cesetti et al. (2013) [12] proposed using sensitivity maps (derivatives of monochromatic fluxes with respect to atmospheric parameters) to rank spectral features. They searched for features that could predict effective temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity. Sarro et al (2018) [13] expands on previous studies by including a broader range of luminosity classes and training a genetic algorithm regression model on optimal spectral features, and using cross-validation to minimize overfitting. They have achieved an average uncertainty of greater 200 K on average, when predicting effective surface temperature and an uncertainty of 0.663 dex when predicting $\log g$ and that of 0.440 dex when predicting metallicity at 50 SNR.

Our work aims the determination of stellar parameters with more accuracy than previously accomplished by employing ever-increasing arsenal of powerful computing resources and robust machine learning techniques. We aim to create a neural network of medium density with a non-linear activation function predicting stellar properties such as effective temperature, metallicity and $\log G$ with uncertainty close to 100 K, 0.3 dex and 0.3 dex respectively, by taking metallic lines in the visible range of 600 – 900 nm for F Type stars, from a random population distribution obtained from the XSHOOTER stellar library. In this work we shall use pseudo-continuum normalisation of the observed stellar spectra, equivalent width calculation of the lines and model fitting of the spectral lines using PHOENIX synthetic spectra. We employ a Bayesian regularization in the neural network, suitable for small and noisy dataset, and principal component analysis to determine the spectral features showing highest correlation with the stellar parameters. By knowing these we can also generate a correlation function showing how the spectral features in the stellar atmosphere of F type stars change throughout the population distribution, consisting dwarfs, subgiants and giants. We have chosen F Type stars because their closeness in properties with the G and K type stars which are like our Sun, known to support a habitable zone. In fact, F type stars are widely accepted to be the most luminous stars, capable of supporting life harbouring planets around them. So, a detailed spectroscopic study predicting their stellar properties such as metallicity, surface gravity and elemental abundance throughout their average lifetime of 2-4 billion years is a necessity to conduct further research on their habitability.

The report is organised as follows: section 2 discusses briefly about the instrument XSHOOTER, by employing which the spectral library was created. Section 3 discusses the methodology employed so far. Section 4 discusses briefly the results. Section 5 concludes the work done and discusses future road map.

2. XSHOOTER Spectrograph and Stellar Spectral Library

The XSHOOTER spectrograph is a highly versatile and powerful instrument mounted on the European Southern Observatory's (ESO) Very Large Telescope (VLT) at the Paranal Observatory in Chile. XSHOOTER is designed to cover an exceptionally broad wavelength range, from the ultraviolet (UV) at approximately 300 nm to the near-infrared (NIR) at 2.5 micrometres (μm), in a single exposure. This capability allows it to capture a comprehensive spectrum of astronomical objects, providing detailed information across a wide range of wavelengths without the need to switch instruments or reconfigure the setup. The spectrograph is composed of three arms—UVB, VIS, and NIR—each optimized for a specific wavelength range. These arms work simultaneously, enabling XSHOOTER to obtain high-resolution spectra (with resolving powers ranging from $R \approx 3,300$ to 18,200) across its full spectral coverage. This broad range and high resolution make XSHOOTER particularly well-suited for a variety of astrophysical applications, including the study of faint and distant objects, the analysis of stellar atmospheres, the characterization of exoplanet atmospheres, and the investigation of interstellar and intergalactic medium properties. The instrument's design incorporates advanced optics, including dichroics that split the incoming light into the three arms, and detectors optimized for sensitivity across the different spectral regions. XSHOOTER's ability to provide continuous spectral coverage with high efficiency has made it a crucial tool in modern astronomy, contributing significantly to our understanding of the universe by enabling detailed and simultaneous observations across the UV, visible, and infrared domains. After two commissioning runs with the UVB and VIS arms only in November 2008 and January 2009, the instrument reached its full configuration in March 2009 and has been in science operations since October 2009.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of XSHOOTER

The XSHOOTER Stellar Spectral Library (XSL) is an extensive and high-quality library of stellar spectra, created using the XSHOOTER spectrograph on the Very Large Telescope (VLT) at the European Southern Observatory (ESO) in Chile. The library covers a broad range of stellar types,

including stars of various spectral classes, luminosity classes, and metallicities, providing a comprehensive dataset for stellar population synthesis, galactic archaeology, and stellar astrophysics. XSL is particularly distinguished by its wide wavelength coverage, spanning from the ultraviolet (UV) through the optical to the near-infrared (NIR) regions, roughly from 300 nm to 2.5 micrometres, all obtained simultaneously with high spectral resolution. This wide spectral range allows astronomers to analyse key diagnostic features across different parts of the stellar spectrum, enabling detailed studies of stellar atmospheres and the derivation of fundamental parameters such as effective temperature, surface gravity, and chemical abundances. The library's high resolution and quality, combined with the diversity of stellar types, make it an invaluable resource for modelling the integrated light of stellar populations, interpreting observations of distant galaxies, and refining theoretical models of stellar evolution. XSL has been widely used in various astrophysical research areas, including the study of star clusters, the calibration of other instruments, and the improvement of stellar models, making it a cornerstone for many modern astronomical studies. [14] [15]

Figure 2: Distribution of Stars in XSHOOTER Stellar Spectral Library

The first data release (DR1) contained UVB and VIS spectra for more than 200 stars. The second data release (DR2) of XSL covers the full X-shooter range (UVB to NIR), but is arm-separated, and contains 813 observations of 666 stars. The third data release (DR3) contains 830 stellar spectra of 683 stars. The DR3 spectra are arm-combined to the full wavelength range of the X-shooter spectrograph, and both original and galactic dust extinction corrected spectra are available. It also covers most of the HR diagram with spectral types between O and M, as well as AGB stars. [16] [17]

In our work we are analyzing the stars of DR2 dataset, and also soon expand our model to DR3 as well. The physical parameters of the stars in DR2 have been taken from Gaia Survey DR2.

3. Methodology

3.1 Spectral Preprocessing

To begin analysis of the observed spectra, one must first ensure some preliminary preprocessing steps to be completed on the observed spectra. This is necessary to have the observed spectra in the same format as the synthetic spectra. Because only then the synthetic model spectra can be used to fit the spectral features in observed spectra. The steps are specifically bringing the observed and synthetic spectra into the identical spectral resolution, sampling, wavelength range and radial velocity correction. We use a spectral analysis software [iSpec](#) to do the tasks (Blanco-Cuaresma et al (2014), Blanco-Cuaresma (2019)). [18] [19]

First, we perform the wavelength range reduction on the observed XSHOOTER and synthetic PHOENIX spectra by choosing a wavelength region of 600 nm – 1000 nm, using iSpec. Next, spectral resampling is important because the observed spectra from XSHOOTER has uneven wavelength steps. One must homogenise the wavelength steps and match it with that of the synthetic spectra for actual analysis. Data resampling by interpolation is a crucial technique in data analysis, particularly in the context of time series, signal processing, and spatial data analysis. It involves creating new data points within the range of an existing dataset, effectively increasing the resolution or filling in gaps in the data. Interpolation works by estimating the values at these new points based on the known values of the surrounding data. This method is widely used when working with datasets that are incomplete, have irregular intervals, or require finer granularity, like we have in the observed spectra, with inhomogeneous wavelength steps. We resample the synthetic and observed spectra by quadratic spline interpolation choosing wavelength step 0.001 using the iSpec because of their smoothing effect. Spline interpolation involves fitting a piecewise polynomial function, called a spline, through a set of data points. The polynomials are chosen not only to pass through the data points but also to ensure that the resulting curve is smooth at the joins between segments, meaning that the first and second derivatives of the curve are continuous across the entire data range.

Figure 3: XSHOOTER spectrum before resampling (left); after resampling (right)

After resampling we have to match the resolutions of the synthetic and observed spectra, in order to make any analysis of the absorption line profiles from any spectral library. In order to do so we have to first identify the radial and barycentric velocity of the star with respect to our solar system from the line profiles to find out the original resolution of the spectra, in order to degrade and match the resolution of the observed stellar spectra from the XSHOOTER Stellar Library and that of synthetic spectra of PHOENIX.

Stars which are moving toward or away from us, we must consider the Doppler effect. We should see all the spectral lines of moving stars shifted toward the red end of the spectrum if the star is moving away from us, or toward the blue (violet) end if it is moving toward us. The greater the shift, the faster the star is moving. Such motion, along the line of sight between the star and the observer, is called radial velocity and is usually measured in kilometers per second. We correct this velocity by precise measurement of the doppler shift, obtaining the velocity and follow-up correction. We do this using the iSpec.

Figure 4: Radial Velocity causes Doppler shift in spectral lines

The generation of the velocity profile is done by an implementation of the cross-match correlation algorithm which sum up the spectrum's fluxes (f) multiplied by a template function 'p':

$$C(v) = \sum_{lines} \sum_{pix} p(pix, v) \cdot flux(pix) \quad Eq. 1$$

- Calculate C(v), where p(pix,v) is varied from a lower to an upper velocity in fixed steps.
- Normalize C(v)

The 'p' function represents the fraction of the line of a template spectrum (which depends on the spectral type of the star) that falls on a given pixel at a given velocity.

iSpec includes an internal template, which corresponds to a synthetic spectrum of a star with T_{eff} 5777.0, gravity ($\log g$) 4.44 and metallicity 0.02 (solar type) which has been generated by using SPECTRUM, atomic data extracted from the VALD database (350 to 11000 nm) and MARCS model atmospheres. In case that another ground-based observed spectrum is used as template, it is recommended to clean the regions that may be affected by telluric lines.

In the case of selecting the option of using atomic lines, a mask is used instead of a template which means that the 'p' function has values only on the peak of the line and the value corresponds to the depth of the line. The possible masks line lists are:

Narval Sun (370 to 1048 nm), Solar and Arcturus atlas (372 to 926 nm), HARPS/SOPHIE A0, F0, G2, K0, K5, M5 (375 to 680 nm)

Figure 5: Radial Velocity correction by measurement of doppler shift of atomic lines using iSpec

Internally, for the cross-correlation process, iSpec creates a mask from the given line list with a user defined size. If one or more mask lines fall into one range, the max depth is assigned as the mask value (otherwise it will be zero).

Afterwards, it re-samples the mask uniformly in terms of velocity by using the specified velocity step (recommended to be half of the mask size). This implies that the distance between the elements in the mask is variable in wavelength but constant in velocity (depends on the mask size specified by the user).

The following formula is used for determining the wavelength ranges: $\lambda_{i+1} = \lambda_i + \lambda_i \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-v/c}{1+v/c}} \right)$

The last step, what remains in preprocessing is matching the spectral resolution. Resolution matching in astronomical spectra is a crucial process in the analysis and comparison of spectral data obtained from different instruments or observations under varying conditions. Astronomical spectra contain detailed information about the physical properties of celestial objects, such as their composition, temperature, velocity, and more. However, different spectrographs and telescopes have different resolving powers, leading to spectra with varying levels of detail (or resolution). To accurately compare or combine spectra from different sources, it's essential to match their resolutions. We degrade the resolution of the synthetic spectra and the observed spectra to 15000, by Gaussian Kernel method using iSpec. For each flux value, the process will define a window based on the FWHM size which depends on the original and target resolution, build a gaussian using the sigma value and the wavelength values of the spectra window and finally convolve the spectra window with the gaussian and save the convolved value.

Figure 6: Resolution matching of PHOENIX spectrum (brown) and XSHOOTER spectrum (blue). Shown: before matching (left) and after matching(right).

3.2 Definition of Continuum

To determine the stellar parameters such as surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity, calculation of equivalent width of spectral features is required. For that, a continuum definition is required. Basically, the continuum of the radiation emitted from the photosphere of the stars are the radiation coming from the radiative zone, without getting reabsorbed by the interior layers. Ideally, the energy distribution of the radiation emitted by a star can be approximated by a blackbody radiation curve. The continuous spectrum can be thought of as coming from the hot surface of the star. Atoms in the atmosphere above the surface absorb certain characteristic wavelengths of this radiation, leaving dark “gaps” at the corresponding points in the spectrum, which are referred to as spectral features or spectral lines. In reality, however there is no such sharp separation between surface and atmosphere. All layers emit and absorb radiation, but the net result of these processes is that less energy is radiated at the wavelengths of the absorption lines. The accuracy of measurement of the equivalent width stands upon the most accurate determination of stellar continuum. However, in practice the continuum is difficult to define, especially because of multiplicity and overcrowding of spectral lines in high-resolution spectra, as well as intermixing of multiple spectral lines and line broadening.

Therefore, approximation of the continuum is necessary, when actual continuum is not known. For that purpose, pseudo-continuum has to be used. Pseudo-continuum is an approximated mathematical function, containing information for the construction of actual continuum, when original continuum is not exactly known. Adapted to the specific application they scale the intensity of the pseudo-continuum with the embedded absorptions proportionally to an appropriate new level. By the linear scaling the continuum-related measurement categories – peak absorption intensity P of a line profile and equivalent width EW – remain unchanged.

$$P_{absorption} = \frac{I_{abs,original}}{I_{cont,original}} = \frac{I_{abs,pseudo}}{I_{cont,pseudo}} \quad Eq. 2$$

Here, intensity of absorption line is I_{abs} and intensity of corresponding continuum is I_{cont} . Therefore, consequently, the equivalent widths of the lines calculated from original continuum and pseudo-continuum should be equivalent.

$$EQ_{pseudo} = EQ_{original} \quad Eq. 3$$

There are numerous ways, a pseudo-continuum can be defined. Some major ways of them are:

- a) Making a pseudo-continuum by taking pre-defined nearest continuum regions on the either side of a spectral line. The continuum regions can be obtained from literature, empirically determined either from photometry or other methods. This method has been used for determination of stellar parameters by measurement of EQs from this definition of pseudo-continuum. (Rojas-Ayala et al (2012), Cesetti et al (2013), Newton et al (2015)) [10] [12]
- b) Fitting a pseudo-continuum by a mathematical function such as spline, or polynomial.
- c) Defining a pseudo-continuum from a synthetic spectrum.
- d) Defining a pseudo-continuum manually overseeing the region devoid of line regions. (Sarro et al (2018))

In our work, we have chosen the modified technique of pseudo-continuum fitting, given by iSpec tool. (Blanco-Cuaresma 2014,2019). In this technique, a median filter (to reduce the noise effects) and a maximum filter (to avoid absorption lines) is applied with windows of sizes specified by the user (the filtering can also be done in the reverse order: max+median). It may be useful to fine tune the window sizes to change the continuum placement, since the most convenient values can depend on the signal-to-noise ratio and spectral type of the star.

The spectral resolution can be specified to optimize the process (oversampling slows down the computation), and the spectrum will be homogeneously re-sampled with a wavelength step equal to the minimum wavelength divided by the resolution. If no resolution is indicated, the spectrum will be re-sampled using the median wavelength step (the fitting process assumes a constant wavelength step, thus the re-sampling ensures that condition).

We fit a second order polynomial to the spectrum with median wavelength step of 0.005 nm and maximum wavelength selection of 7 nm. We have determined these values of the wavelength steps, as we have found they are optimum values for generating the continuum, without overlapping any of the spectral features.

Figure 7: Fitted continuum(right) with properties chosen(left).

To automatically detect and ignore strong absorption lines (for which the maximum filter is not enough), iSpec implements a probabilistic mechanism that can be controlled by setting a greater or lower probability threshold. This mechanism expects that the rate of change of the filtered fluxes should be similar (in chunks 20 times the max window size, with a minimum value of 10 nm), if a dramatic change is found then it is probable that is due to a strong absorption line and these points will be ignored. A higher probability threshold will accept less outlying rate changes and vice-versa.

With continuum obtained, we divide the continuum with the spectra and obtain the continuum normalized spectra. With our spectra processed by the above steps, we can proceed towards the principal analysis by the help of synthetic PHOENIX spectra. Before we proceed with our analysis a brief talk on PHOENIX synthetic spectra is necessary.

Figure 8: Continuum Normalized Spectra: Observed XShooter Spectra (blue), Synthetic Spectra (brown)

3.3 PHOENIX Model and Synthetic Spectra

PHOENIX is a spherically symmetric special relativistic Non-LTE (Non- Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium) radiative transfer code originally given as new solution to the special relativistic radiative transfer equation by Hauschildt in 1992, and since then developed to explain diverse atmospheric phenomena from expanding shells of ejected materials from novae and supernovae as well as describe stellar photosphere of stars of almost all spectral classes and types. The original PHOENIX code originated from the Discrete Ordinate Matrix Exponential (DOME) method given by (Hauschildt 1992) [20] in which space parameter is discretized in concentric spherical shells, then the solution for discretized intensity in each shell is calculated using recursion methods choosing suitable initial condition and finally the total intensity is found by interpolation. The discretized version of solution enabled the matrix formulation of the radiative transfer problem, which allows for parallel processing of each of the rows of the matrix using modern parallel computing thus making the computing time significantly less. PHOENIX code was developed in 1994 by Allard and Hauschildt [21] to explain spectra of M Dwarfs, as well as Brown Dwarfs, between surface temperatures 1500 to 4000 K, surface gravity with $\log g$ between 3.5 to 5.5 and metallicity between -4 to +0.5 dex. In this work, 26 ionization stages of 39 elements (H, He, Li, Be, B, C, N, O, F, Ne, Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, Ar, K, Ca, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ga, Kr, Rb, Sr, Y, Zr, Nb, Ba, and La) as well as 105 molecules were included. Particle and charge conservation in each layer of an ideal gas was assumed for solving the equation of state. The dissociation constants of diatomic and polyatomic molecules were calculated internally by means of a Saha-like derivation. The model was extended to a grid of plane-parallel model atmospheres for dwarf stars of almost all spectral types ($\log g \geq 3.5$) and in the

temperature range : 3000 to 10,000 K. . Same models were calculated for lower surface gravity stars (giants) with $\log g$: 0 to 3.5.(Hauschildt et al 1998, 1999). [22]

Figure 10: PHOENIX Model Spectra ($T_{\text{eff}} = 6100$ K, $\text{Fe}/\text{H} = 0.0$, $\text{Log } G = 4.0$)

Figure 9: Distribution of stellar masses for different effective temperatures T_{eff} and surface gravities $\log g$, colour-coded in units of solar mass from 0 M_{SUN} (black) to 25 M_{SUN} (white).

We are using a high-resolution synthetic spectral grid, that was calculated using latest PHOENIX (version 16) -AMES-cond-v2.6 by Husser et al (2013). [23]The synthetic spectra cover the wavelength range from 500 Å to 5.5 μm with resolutions of $R = 500\,000$ in the optical and near IR, $R = 100\,000$ in the IR and $\Delta\lambda = 0.1\text{Å}$ in the UV. The parameter space covers $2300\text{ K} \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 12\,000\text{ K}$, $0.0 \leq \log g \leq +6.0$, $-4.0 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq +1.0$, and $-0.2 \leq [\alpha/\text{Fe}] \leq +1.2$. All model atmospheres were calculated in a spherical mode with 64 layers. Local thermodynamic equilibrium was said to be assumed for all the models in the library.

The Astrophysical Chemical Equilibrium Solver (ACES, Barman 2012) equation of state (EOS) was used starting with PHOENIX version 16 is a state-of-the-art treatment of the chemical equilibrium in a stellar atmosphere. It uses the method of Smith & Missen (1982) with new experimental and theoretical thermodynamical data (Barman 2012) for 839 species (84 elements, 289 ions, 249 molecules, 217 condensates). In each layer, the chemical equilibrium for all used atomic and

molecular species was computed in dependence on the pressure, temperature, and density. After computing the atmospheric structure with the equations of radiation and hydrodynamics, a new chemical equilibrium is calculated in a second step. Microturbulence and convection was also considered in calculating grid.

The element abundances for the grid are scaled solar abundances taken from Asplund et al. (2009), where the abundances in both the photosphere and in meteorites are given.

Table 1: Sampling of the spectral grid

Range [\AA]	Sampling
500–3000	$\Delta\lambda = 0.1\text{\AA}$
3000–25 000	$R \approx 500\ 000$
25 000–55 000	$R \approx 100\ 000$

Table 2: Parameter Space of the grid

Variable	Range	Step size
T_{eff} [K]	2300 – 7000	100
	7000 – 12000	200
Log g	0.0 – +6.0	0.5
[Fe/H]	-4.0 – 2.0	1.0
	-2.0 – +1.0	0.5
$[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$	-0.2 – +1.2	0.2

3.4 Creation of the data set from spectral features table

For analysis, only slit-loss corrected spectra of F Type Stars were taken; spectral line features were compared with that of the PHOENIX synthetic spectra, of comparable stellar parameters. We identified the line profiles by cross matching with the synthetic line profiles obtained from the PHOENIX synthetic spectra.

First, the common cross-matched atomic line profiles in the F Type stars' spectra were identified and selected by generating line masks of the corresponding line profiles from the synthetic spectra from PHOENIX grid.

Next, for each defined line masks, a Gaussian was fitted according to given parameters using iSpec. It requires that the spectrum is corrected by its radial velocity and fitted continuum. The parameters of the Gaussian are set by iSpec, according to the resolution of the spectra.

Next, fitted lines was then cross-matched with an atomic line list SPECTRUM and if the difference between the theoretical and measured wavelength peak is smaller than a given limit, the atomic information will be linked to line region. In case there is more than one line within the limit, the line with the greatest theoretical equivalent width (for solar atmospheric values) will be chosen.

Finally, iSpec will cross-match the lines with a telluric line list to mark with a * symbol if any line may be affected by telluric lines.

We choose the lines with depths, at least 10 percent of the continuum, with chosen resolution of 15000. All telluric affected lines are rejected as well as second-derivative and third derivative were chosen to fix the start and end points of the lines accurately.

Figure 12: Properties selected for line mask fitting.

Figure 11: Cross-matched spectral lines of observed spectrum (blue) from XSHOOTER, fitted by line masks identified using PHOENIX synthetic spectrum (brown), lines identified with SPECTRUM line list(300nm-1000nm)

The Equivalent Widths of the fitted lines are then calculated using iSpec Program. The EW represents the strength of an absorption line, and it is defined as the width, in wavelength units, that a rectangular stripe of height I_c , in intensity units, would have if it had the same area as the actual line or—in other words—the wavelength interval that would be covered by a hypothetical, perfectly opaque absorption feature that removes the same amount of energy from the continuum flux.

Mathematically:

$$EQ = \sum_i \Delta\lambda_i \frac{I_c - I_i}{I_c}$$

where $\Delta\lambda_i$ is the (constant) pixel size, I_c is the continuum level at the wavelength of the i th pixel, and I_i is the actual flux received by the i th pixel.

Figure 13: Equivalent Width

A total of 51 F Type Stars (List given in Table 3) from the XShooter Stellar Library Data Release 2 has been analysed likewise using the methodology discussed and the equivalent widths of the important metallic lines of Fe 1, Fe 2, Ca 2, Si 1, Si 2, Mg 1 and Cr 1 (List given in Table 4) has been calculated with the stars grouped into groups of corresponding surface gravity and metallicity value classes. The Stars have been binned into surface gravity classes of $\text{Log } g \sim 0.5-2.5, 1-3, 4-4.5$ and the metallicity classes of $\text{Fe}/\text{H} \sim -2, -1.5, -1, -0.5, 0.0, +0.5$. Next, regression analysis has been carried out for all of the bins. Regression analysis over surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity has been done using neural network model, which we shall discuss in the next section. The Equivalent width table has been used for the input dataset and the stellar parameters has been used as the target dataset.

Table 3: F Type stars' list, from XSHOOTER Spectral Library, with stellar parameters given, that has been used in our model.

Name	Tem p	Log g	Fe/H	Name	Tem p	Log g	Fe/H
HD 17072	5441	2.59	-1	HD 172506	7096	4.02	-0.02
HD 160365	6237	3.41	0.08	HD 191709	6672	3.89	0.27
HD 205202	6572	4.12	-0.47	HD 196125	7246	3.89	0.02
BD+26 4251	6002	4.36	-1.28	HD 161227	7238	3.77	0.44
HD 204155	5761	4.02	-0.68	HD 164115	6792	3.86	0.15
HD 196892	6028	4.17	-0.99	HD 172365	5989	1.3	0.12
HD 175805	6408	3.72	0.39	CD-30 18140	6214	3.79	-2.03
HD 167278	6491	3.82	-0.24	HD 196218	6162	4.19	-0.1
HD 52298	6351	4.6	-0.84	HD 30743	6352	4.12	-0.44
* 25 Mon	6426	3.21	0.44	HD 48616	6380	1.86	-0.08
HD 138290	6866	4.21	-0.03	HD 60319	5922	4.22	-0.82
HD 218502	6161	3.96	-1.86	HD 74000	6218	4.25	-1.96
V* V1401 Aql	6406	1.81	-1.12	HD 84937	6302	4.04	-2.12
HD 176851	6834	3.7	0.42	BD+24 1676	6233	4.13	-2.44
HD 144172	6311	4.07	-0.44	BD+25 1981	6630	4.6941	-1.444
HD 205555	7257	3.7	0.22	HD 93487	5250	1.8	-1.1
HD 161149	6899	3.82	0.38	BD+29 2091	5774	4.52	-1.96
HD 14938	6155	4.07	-0.35	V* LN Hya	6033	0.63	-0.65
HD 19304	6582	4.22	-0.45	V* MO Hya	7595	4.28	-1
HD 25532	5395	2.08	-1.32	HD 102634	6293	4.2	0.2
HD 88737	6144	3.89	0.16	HD 109443	6791	4.24	-0.6
HD 78737	6447	3.82	-0.63	HD 110885	5440	2.54	-1.44
HD 41661	6519	3.79	0.15				
V* UZ Cen	6492	2.42	0.27				
HD 106038	6124	4.29	-1.35				
HD 108177	6114	4.3	-1.66				
HD 128429	6383	4.22	-0.12				
V* U Nor	5568	1.13	0.17				
HD 142575	6756	4.21	-0.72				

Table 4: Spectral lines used to calculate equivalent width table, which has been used as input to our model.

Line profile	Wavelength(nm)
Fe 1	605.5992
Fe 1	606.5482
Fe 1	607.8491
Ca 1	610.2716
Ca 1	612.2217
Fe 1	613.6615
Fe 1	613.7689
Ca 1	616.2173
Ca 1	616.9563
Fe 1	619.1558
Fe 2	623.8378

Fe 1	624.6313
Fe 1	625.4253
Fe 1	633.683
Si 2	637.1355
Fe 1	643.0856
Fe 2	645.6391
Fe 1	667.7997
Ca 1	671.7681
Fe 1	684.1339
Fe 1	685.5161
Ca 1	732.6145
Fe 1	738.6334
Mg 1	738.7689
Fe 1	744.5749
Cr 1	746.2378
Fe 1	751.102
Fe 1	758.6018
Si 1	794.4001
Fe 1	846.8407
Ca 2	866.2141
Mg 1	880.6756
Fe 1	882.422

3.5 Neural Network Model

3.5.1 A brief introduction to neural networks

Neural networks are the class of machine learning algorithms proven to be one of the most potent approaches in data analysis by far. A simple machine learning model consists of the activation function, which takes the given training dataset as discrete inputs and outputs a predicted value. The expected value is fitted to actual training data, already provided by minimizing the difference between the expected value and the original value, minimizing the cost function over many iterations, and finally getting the function's parameters. Once the trained parameters of the activation function are obtained, it can predict the output with sufficient accuracy. A neural network consists of many layers of such activation functions, called 'neurons' or 'nodes,' where each neuron in each layer takes the output from every neuron from the previous layer and gives output to be taken as input for the neurons of the next layer. Anatomically, the very first layer of a neural network consists of the input features selected from the data set for the particular prediction required. The layers that follow, which calculate the weights of the model for prediction, are called hidden layers. The last layer, the output layer, predicts the required parameters based on the input parameters already fed as input using the trained weights. Each layer consists of the function parameters called 'weights,' which are found by the minimization of the cost function, just like in the case of a basic machine learning regression model, the only difference being the weights are computed sequentially for each of the layers meaning the weights of the final layer before the output layer is learned first, then using the values we learn the weights of the previous layer till we reach the first layer. This is known as backpropagation.

When the weights are computed, they are used by the activation function of the neurons of the very first hidden layer to output the predicted value, which is taken as input by the next hidden layer, which then outputs the predicted value to be taken as input by the next layer until the final output layer gives the final predicted value. This is called forward propagation.

Figure 15: Back-propagation learning

Figure 14: A Neural Network

Each iteration consists of such a back propagation and a forward propagation, by which the values of the weights are calculated with sufficient accuracy. For our purpose we input the equivalent width of the spectral features in the XSHOOTER stellar spectra of the stars as input features, and stellar parameters of effective surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity logarithm as output features or targets/labels. The model can be trained to predict the given stellar parameters and finding correlation of the spectral features with the stellar parameters.

For accurately testing the efficiency and robustness of the model, the model trained on the input dataset needed to be tested. If the accuracy is low then the model is trained indefinitely until required or best possible accuracy is achieved. For that purpose, some amount of data is kept aside to do the test purpose and it is called test dataset. Further for training the model for best possible result, one need to keep changing the parameters of the model like number of regression nodes, layers, rate at which training is done etc called hyper-parameters. To tune the hyperparameter for optimum result

one must use some train data to measure the effectiveness of the parameters used in each iteration for validation. This is known as validation dataset.

However, any machine learning model not just neural networks suffers from a flaw called overfitting. Overfitting occurs when an algorithm fits too closely or even exactly to its training data, resulting in a model that can't make accurate predictions or conclusions from any data other than the training data. When machine learning algorithms are constructed, they leverage a sample dataset to train the model. However, when the model trains for too long on sample data or when the model is too complex, it can start to learn the “noise,” or irrelevant information, within the dataset. When the model memorizes the noise and fits too closely to the training set, the model becomes “overfitted,” and it is unable to generalize well to new data. If a model cannot generalize well to new data, then it will not be able to perform the classification or prediction tasks that it was intended for.

Another difficulty in training data models is underfitting. It is a scenario in data science where a data model is unable to capture the relationship between the input and output variables accurately, generating a high error rate on both the training set and unseen data. Underfitting occurs when a model is too simple, which can be a result of a model needing more training time, more input features, or less regularization.

The solution for overfitting is regularization. Regularization encompasses a range of techniques to correct for overfitting in machine learning models. Regularization provides this increased generalizability at the sake of increased training error. In other words, regularization methods typically lead to less accurate predictions on training data but more accurate predictions on test data. Basically, under the context of neural network, overfitting occurs when weights of the nodes keep increasing arbitrary in value after each iteration resulting in inaccurate results. To overcome this the weights are needed to be minimized without increasing indefinitely and converge to a particular value, predicting the optimum results. For that purpose, a term involving weights is added to the cost function, with a parameter known as lambda or regularization constant.

Figure 16: Overfitting and Underfitting illustrated

We shall discuss here only such method, which we have used in our model and that is the Bayesian regularization method in the next section.

3.5.2 Our Bayesian Regularized Neural Network Model

The objective of our training process will be to minimize the sum of squared errors: $E_D = \sum (t - a)^2$ where t is the target(stellar parameters of temperature, metallicity and $\log g$) and a is the neural network's prediction. Typically, training aims to reduce the sum of squared errors $F = E_D$. However, regularization adds an additional term; the objective function becomes $F = \beta E_D + \alpha E_W$, where E_W is the sum of squares of the network weights, and α and β are objective function parameters. The relative size of the objective function parameters dictates the emphasis for training. If $\alpha \ll \beta$, then the training algorithm will drive the errors smaller. If $\alpha \gg \beta$, training will emphasize weight size reduction at the

expense of network errors, thus producing a smoother network response. In the Bayesian framework the weights of the network are considered random variables. After the data is taken, the density function for the weights can be updated according to Bayes' rule: $P(D|W, \beta, M) = \frac{\exp(-\beta E_D + \alpha E_W)}{Z_D(\beta)}$, where D represents the data set, M is the particular neural network model used, and w is the vector of network weights. If we assume that the noise in the training set data is Gaussian and that the prior distribution for the weights is Gaussian, the probability densities can be written as

$$P(D|W, \beta, M) = \frac{\exp(-\beta E_D + \alpha E_W)}{Z_D(\beta)} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Here, $Z_D(\beta)$ is the normalization factor. In this Bayesian framework, the optimal weights should maximize the posterior probability $P(D|W, \beta, M)$. Maximizing the posterior probability is equivalent to minimizing the regularized objective function $\beta E_D + \alpha E_W$. This is known as the Bayesian Regularization. [24] [25]

Figure 17: Our Bayesian Regularized NN Regressor Model for prediction of stellar parameters

Our model has 10 neurons in a single hidden layer with sigmoid activation function: $\frac{2}{(1 + \exp(-2 \cdot n)) - 1}$. We input the calculated equivalent widths of the 32 lines of Fe 1, Fe 2, Ca 1, Ca 2, Mg 1, Cr 1 etc. listed in Table 4 to our neural network and use the 3 physical parameters consisting of surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity logarithm as the target or labels. Next, we employ Bayesian Regularization to the cost function, as already discussed. We use the MATLAB NN Fitter Optimizer for the purpose of fitting. We have run 1000 iterations, which took about 15 seconds.

4. Results

For 1000 iterations, we obtain a training accuracy of 3.79×10^{-5} with final gradient obtained of 0.196. As evident from Figure 18, the test dataset mean squared error is of about an order of 10^4 . Also, it can be noted the minimum test error has been obtained at 1000th iteration, with test error peaking after 700th iteration and then continually decreases gradually to converge to a minimum. Our model's variance is of-course minimized but still very high which is expected because of a very small dataset size and comparatively a very large feature set size. This can be overcome if we increase the dataset size by including interpolated spectral features from the synthetic PHOENIX data set to be part of the input dataset as well. Nonetheless, it is giving us promising result as our model is predicting effective temperature within error margin of close to 200 Kelvin RMSE. It also predicts the metallicity within error margin of 0.35 dex and the logarithm of surface gravity (Log g) within 0.24 dex, which are close to the error margins we were aiming for. Our results offer more accuracy than previously obtained by regression of same physical parameters on M Stars using genetic algorithm feature selection, done by Sarro et al (2018). Our results show the Bayesian regularized NN model gives much better result within a small stellar population taken for study, than many other NN models, applied to the same population, using usual regularization.

Figure 18: Training Performance of our model

Figure 19: Regression results: Plot of actual vs predicted stellar parameters of Training and Test datasets. (Top) Effective Temperature, (Middle) Metallicity (Fe/H) and (Bottom) Surface Gravity ($Log G$)

5. Conclusion

Although we have obtained a model which can predict over small populations of stars with comparatively more accuracy than previous models, we can do better. The RMSE of the predictions of our Bayesian NN model can be further decreased by the following procedures:

- A combined dataset composed of the PHOENIX synthetic spectra, of corresponding physical parameters in the range of that of the observed stellar spectra of F Type stars in the Xshooter stellar spectral library can be created for input dataset to our model. This will help interpolate the equivalent widths of the spectral features and further refine our model greatly improving our prediction accuracy.
- A hyperparameter tuned Bayesian Neural Network Model can give us even better result. Hyper-parameters are model parameters such learning rate, number of neurons in each layer, regularization parameters alpha and beta etc.
- After the completion of the building of the optimum model we can predict over the physical parameter of the F-type stars to build a correlation function of equivalent widths of the spectral features predicting the physical parameters.
- A principal component analysis can be run to predict which lines are most typical in predicting the physical parameters.

References

- [1] R. L. Kurucz, "Model atmospheres for G, F, A, B, and O stars," *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, vol. 40, 1979.
- [2] D. Mihalas, *Stellar atmospheres*, 2d ed., San Francisco: W. H. Freeman, 1978, pp. xx, 632 p..
- [3] D. Mihalas and B. Weibel-Mihalas, *Foundations of radiation hydrodynamics*, New York: Oxford University Press, 1984, pp. xv, 718 p..
- [4] I. Hubeny and T. Lanz, "Non-LTE line-blanketed model atmospheres of hot stars. 1: Hybrid complete linearization/accelerated lambda iteration method," *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 439, 1995.
- [5] M. Asplund, A. A. Nordlund, R. Trampedach, C. A. Prieto and R. F. Stein, "Line formation in solar granulation: I. Fe line shapes, shifts and asymmetries," *Astron. Astrophys.*, vol. 359, pp. 729-742, 2000.
- [6] S. R. F. & A. M. Nordlund, "Solar Surface Convection," *Living Rev. Sol. Phys.*, vol. 6, 2009.
- [7] B.-J. et al., "Automated stellar classification for large surveys: a review of methods and results," 2001.
- [8] P. R. Fiorentin, C. A. L. Bailer-Jones, Y. S. Lee, T. C. Beers, T. Sivarani, R. Wilhelm, C. A. Prieto and J. E. Norris, "Estimation of stellar atmospheric parameters from SDSS/SEGUE spectra," *A&A*, vol. 467, pp. 1373-1387, 2007.

- [9] V. Neves, X. Bonfils, N. C. Santos, X. Delfosse, T. Forveille, F. Allard, C. Natário, C. S. Fernandes and S. Udry, “Metallicity of M dwarfs - II. A comparative study of photometric metallicity scales,” *A&A*, vol. 538, 2012.
- [10] E. R. Newton, D. Charbonneau, J. Irwin and A. W. Mann, “An Empirical Calibration to Estimate Cool Dwarf Fundamental Parameters From h-Band Spectra,” *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 800, 2015.
- [11] A. W. Mann, G. A. Feiden, E. Gaidos, T. Boyajian and K. v. Braun, “How to Constrain Your M Dwarf: Measuring Effective Temperature, Bolometric Luminosity, Mass, and Radius,” *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 804, 2015.
- [12] M. Cesetti, A. Pizzella, V. D. Ivanov, L. Morelli, E. M. Corsini and E. D. Bontà, “The Infrared Telescope Facility (IRTF) spectral library: - Spectral diagnostics for cool stars,” *A&A*, vol. 549, 2013.
- [13] L. M. Sarro, J. Ordieres-Meré, A. Bello-García, A. González-Marcos and E. Solano, “Estimates of the atmospheric parameters of M-type stars: a machine-learning perspective,” *MNRAS*, vol. 476, pp. 1120-1139, 2018.
- [14] A. Arentsen, P. Prugniel, A. Gonneau, A. Lançon, S. Trager, R. Peletier, M. Lyubenova, Y.-P. Chen, J. Falcón Barroso, P. Sánchez Blázquez and A. Vazdekis, “Stellar atmospheric parameters for 754 spectra from the X-shooter Spectral Library,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 627, 2019.
- [15] A. Gonneau, M. Lyubenova, A. Lançon, S. C. Trager, R. F. Peletier, A. Arentsen, Y. P. Chen, P. R. T. Coelho, M. Dries, J. Falcón-Barroso, P. Prugniel, P. Sánchez-Blázquez, A. Vazdekis and K. Verro, “The X-shooter Spectral Library (XSL): Data release 2,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 634, 2020.
- [16] K. Verro, S. C. Trager, R. F. Peletier, A. Lançon, A. Arentsen, Y. P. Chen, P. R. T. Coelho, M. Dries, J. Falcón-Barroso, A. Gonneau, M. Lyubenova, L. Martins, P. Prugniel, P. Sánchez-Blázquez and A. Vazdekis, “Modelling simple stellar populations in the near-ultraviolet to near-infrared with the X-shooter Spectral Library (XSL),” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 661, 2022.
- [17] K. Verro, S. C. Trager, R. F. Peletier, A. Lançon, A. Gonneau, A. Vazdekis, P. Prugniel, Y. P. Chen, P. R. T. Coelho, P. Sánchez-Blázquez, L. Martins, A. Arentsen, M. Lyubenova, J. Falcón-Barroso and M. Dries, “The X-shooter Spectral Library (XSL): Data Release 3,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 660, 2022.
- [18] S. Blanco-Cuaresma, C. Soubiran, U. Heiter and P. Jofré, “Determining stellar atmospheric parameters and chemical abundances of FGK stars with iSpec,” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 569, 2014.
- [19] S. Blanco-Cuaresma, “Modern stellar spectroscopy caveats,” *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, vol. 486, pp. 2075-2101, 2019.
- [20] R. W. P.H. Hauschild, “Solution of the special relativistic equation of radiative transfer in rapidly expanding spherical shells,” *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, vol. 46, pp. 81-98, 1991.

- [21] F. Allard and P. H. Hauschildt, "Model atmospheres for M (sub)dwarf stars. 1: The base model grid," *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 445, 1995.
- [22] P. H. Hauschildt, F. Allard and E. Baron, "THE NEXTGEN MODEL ATMOSPHERE GRID FOR T_{EFF} 3000K-10000K," *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 512, pp. 377-385, 1999.
- [23] T. O. Husser, S. Wende-von Berg, S. Dreizler, D. Homeier, A. Reiners, T. Barman and P. H. Hauschildt, "A new extensive library of PHOENIX stellar atmospheres and synthetic spectra," *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, vol. 553, 2013.
- [24] F. D. Foresee and M. T. Hagan, "Gauss-Newton approximation to Bayesian learning," in *roceedings of International Conference on Neural Networks (ICNN'97)*, Houston, 1997.
- [25] D. J. C. MacKay, "Bayesian Interpolation," in *Maximum Entropy and Bayesian Methods*, Springer, 1992, pp. 39-66.